

Kalman filtered depth prediction using Optical Coherence Tomography for laser bone cutting

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Abstract: Laser osteotomy may benefits patients with minor damage to the bone and accelerated the healing process. However, the lack of depth control is still needed to be overcome. We proposed to use Optical Coherence Tomography imaging for depth control of the laser ablation process. The OCT image provides geometrical information over the ablation spot and enables the measurement of depth in real-time. Additionally, we demonstrated the use of Kalman filter to predict incoming pulse ablation depth and avoid excessive cut than planned. The result shows that the Kalman filter reduced the error between the planned and real ablated depth.

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I. Introduction

The use of lasers in medical applications is still an interesting focus of research in recent years. Lasers have been used in several surgical procedures such as cataracts, endodontic, and tumor removal [1,2]. Particularly in bone surgery, lasers are used due to the advantages such as minor damage to the bone and accelerated the healing process [3]. However, the lack of depth control in laser still needs to be overcome. This depth control will help the surgeon avoid cutting an excessive amount of bone than planned. Several approaches have been proposed to predict the laser ablation process kinematic such as solving the forward and inverse problem [4,5]. However, these methods are impractical and complex. Here, extensive databases of the ablation process condition are needed. It will become complex when we face a heterogenous or multilayered tissue.

This paper proposed to reflect the use of Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) imaging system to monitor the laser ablation process [4,6]. We demonstrated and extended the OCT depth measurement to predict the next incoming pulse ablation depth by employing the Kalman filter [7]. This prediction will help prevent the laser from overcutting the bone, which may arise due to the passive component's delayed response to stop the laser.

II. Material and methods

The combination setup between the Er:YAG ablation laser system (LITETOUCH by Syneron, working wavelength of 2.94 μm) and the OCT imaging system is illustrated in Fig 1. Both laser beams were combined with a dichroic mirror. An optical beam shutter (Thorlabs SH1) is placed in front of the Er:YAG laser to stop the ablation laser pulse.

Figure 1. Combination setup between the Er:YAG ablation laser and OCT. Both laser beams were combined with a dichroic mirror.

Figure 2. Example of the ablated bone (left) and the OCT image scanned over the ablated crater (right). In the OCT images, the measured depth was defined as the averaged distance between circle (a) and (b) to the bottom of the crater at circle (c). Meanwhile, circle (d) represents the predicted bone surface for the incoming laser ablation pulse.

B-scan image frames were streamed with a custom made OCT system equipped with an Axsun swept laser source ($\lambda_0 = 1060 \text{ nm}$, $\Delta\lambda = 100 \text{ nm}$, and sweep rate = 100 kHz). The

corresponding lateral and axial resolutions were 44 μm and 10 μm , respectively. The system enables image acquisition with a size of 1024 x 400 pixels (3.6 mm depth x 5.6 mm lateral) and previews the ablation process in real-time. We set the OCT system's acquisition rate to 8.5 frames per second after averaging 20 frames to provide a good image quality.

The bone surface was extracted from the OCT image by employing the Canny edge detection algorithm [8]. The measured depth was defined as the relative distance between the adjacent surface and the bottom of the crater (illustrated on the right side of Fig. 2). We then used the depth measurement as feedback to close the optical beam shutter before the measured or predicted depth reached the targeted depth.

I.1. Kalman filter depth prediction

Kalman filter produces estimates of unknown variables that tend to be more accurate than those based on a single measurement alone. This filter has been used in numerous technologies, particularly in distance measurement sensors [7]. The Kalman filter used in the experiment was based on the constant velocity model, which assumes that the velocity is constant during a sampling interval and expressed as

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_t \\ v_t \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \Delta t \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} x_{t-1} + w_t \quad (1)$$

where x_t , v_t and w_t are the predicted actual state of depth, ablation rate, and process noise at time t , respectively. This model has been used in many applications because of its versatility, effectiveness, and simplicity.

I.1. Experiment setup

The tissues used in this experiment were porcine femur bone samples. We tested the feedback system for cutting the bone with the targeted depth of 703.13 μm and 1406.25 μm . We also compared the result when we employ the Kalman filter for prediction. The laser ablation energy was set to 450 mJ per pulse. The bone was ablated in repetition rates of 1 Hz, 5 Hz, and 10 Hz, respectively.

III. Results and discussion

The results of the experiment are shown in Table 1. In the absence of the Kalman filter, the feedback system always passes the targeted depth. These errors mainly due to the communication delay of the optical shutter. Furthermore—when the Er:YAG laser repetition rate was set to 10 Hz—the slower acquisition rate of the OCT also contributes to error, because it may miss an ablation pulse measurement.

Furthermore, the results show that the Kalman filter significantly reduces the error of ablation. In a repetition rate of 1 Hz, the filter stopped the ablation even before the targeted depth (premature stop), which indicates that the incoming pulse will ablate deeper than the targeted depth. However, similarly to the absence of the Kalman filter, the feedback system exceeds the targeted depth when the laser repetition rate was set to 5 Hz and 10 Hz.

Table 1. Final measured depth after stopping the ablation using the proposed feedback system. A negative error value indicates premature stop.

Kalman Filter	Target Depth (μm)	Repetition rate	Measured Depth (μm)	Prediction Error (μm)
Off	703.13	1 Hz	712.828 \pm 10.616	9.698 \pm 10.616
		5 Hz	738.422 \pm 12.909	35.292 \pm 12.909
		10 Hz	774.492 \pm 13.977	71.362 \pm 13.977
	1406.25	1 Hz	1413.703 \pm 12.767	7.453 \pm 12.767
		5 Hz	1436.906 \pm 13.448	30.656 \pm 13.448
		10 Hz	1469.813 \pm 8.114	63.563 \pm 8.114
On	703.13	1 Hz	691.523 \pm 4.313	-11.607 \pm 4.313
		5 Hz	716.484 \pm 16.704	13.354 \pm 16.704
		10 Hz	729.352 \pm 23.187	26.222 \pm 23.187
	1406.25	1 Hz	1383.539 \pm 18.626	-22.711 \pm 18.626
		5 Hz	1414.898 \pm 27.777	8.648 \pm 27.777
		10 Hz	1437.188 \pm 23.734	30.938 \pm 23.734

IV. Conclusions and future work

We demonstrated the use of OCT to monitor the laser ablation process and the Kalman filter to predict incoming ablation depth to reduced cutting an excessive amount of bone than planned. However, further investigation is needed to demonstrate the benefit of using the Kalman filter for deeper ablation prediction. In the future, we will investigate more in finding a better kinematic model of the Kalman filter. We will also explore how to overcome the response delay problem (e.g., increasing our OCT system's acquisition rate and defining an offset to the target depth).

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